

The Effect of Gratitude On Well-Being

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *This review aims to notice the positive outcomes in life when there is gratitude. It gives a sense of pleasantness when there is intrinsic thankfulness. When do we consciously appreciate and thank the blessings that we have been bestowed with? What could come out of it? This review study is about understanding the nature or virtuousness about gratitude. Studies based on gratitude as an intervention had a positive affect between hassles and gratitude groups. A comprehensive review study on 42 researches in 12 years have also established positive relationship between physical health and gratitude. Studies had variables ranging from health behavior, interpersonable variable, mental health, optimism, pro social behavior, satisfaction, forgiveness, support, excitement, hope, etc. It was found that appreciation of positive aspects in life was directly proportional to gratitude. In all the studies conducted globally on Gratitude under different functional elements like psychopathology, social sciences, school college students, adolescents, in other racial contexts, it has had a positive outcome. Studies have evaluated the quality of wellbeing. Gratefulness enhances happiness and gives hope.*

Design/Methodology/Approach: *This Systematic literature review was done by means of researching different databases like Mendeley, Google Scholar and ResearchGate.*

Findings/Result: *The benefits of gratitude, its relation to well-being have been studied. Around 25 reviews have been researched and found that Gratitude has a positive impact. Gender differences and general wellbeing have been examined in early adolescents. It is found that only few studies have been done in the Indian context.*

Paper Type: *Systematic review based literature*

Keywords: Gratitude, Grateful, Well-Being, Happiness, Positive Psychology

1. INTRODUCTION:

Offering thanks is an age old concept that exist in almost many traditions around the world. Kadazan festival in Malaysia, Chuseok Harvest festival in Korea, Thanksgiving in Canada and the US, Emtedankfest in Germany, Harvest Moon festival in China, Sukkot in Israel, Pongal in India are few but not all. The act of saying grace before eating every meal is an act of expressing gratitude. Studies have proved that gratitude is positively related to good health and well-being [1]. Ethnic variation in gratitude was present among Latino Americans and East Asian Americans. Perceived stress and loneliness were found to be lesser than the self-esteem that budded out of gratitude and wellbeing. It was found that the Latino Americans showed a higher sense of health and well-being in the study against the East Americans. The Latino Americans rated their gratitude experience based on desirability, frequency and intensity of expression higher than the east Asian Americans. Further research for diverse ethnic groups were also recommended [1] A cross Sectional quantitative research in Jakarta yielded similar results among 388 undergraduate University students. It was found that gratitude contributed to almost about 40 percent of well-being/ Life experiences and constant appreciation of it played a major role in its contribution. Positive emotions, relationships and accomplishments were contributing factors [2]. A qualitative review which integrated the model of gratitude and well-being and health reviewed 42 researches for 12 years and the relationship between gratitude and physical health was found. Lavelock et al have modelled their theories on the three components that make up

for the well-being. Health behavior, interpersonal variable and mental health and additions from other literature have been integrated in his work. Other traits and features both positive and adverse have been incorporated with interventions leading to gratitude in a Christian context leaving room for potential research [3]. Differences in subjective well-being among gender in early adolescents showed a positive relationship. Gratitude and its benefits was studied in depth among 154 boys and girls students. A comparison between the genders resulted in boys benefitting more than girls. It showed positive relationship for forgiveness, excitement, hope, pride, etc. Gratitude had a positive impact on health with the help of relational fulfillment. Many variables like optimism, pro social behavior, satisfaction, support on a subjective and objective outlook resulted in positive relationship between gratitude and wellbeing. [4]. 315 male Iranian soldiers participated in a study which aimed at establishing a relationship between mental health and inherent gratitude. General Health Questionnaire, perceived Stress scale assessments and WHO assessments served as datasets for bootstrap estimation Method. This mediated a direct correlation between dispositional gratitude and stress and mental health [5].

A review about the well-being among 221 young adolescents was studied. The concept of counting blessings was initially unclear with them. A pre and post intervention with an experimental and control group indicated being effective. Subjective well-being and psychological outcomes were evaluated as an initial post-test. Gratitude, optimism brought down the negativity. A three week window for another round of post intervention helped them realize the positive influence it had on their school experience. Being grateful positively enhanced the relationship between gratitude and general well-being and satisfaction. [6]. In a Spanish gratitude intervention program by Emmons and McCullough, this was a counting blessings study. The three conditions that were tested on were hassles, an event and gratitude. This experiment altered design from the original study by introducing and changing the pre-test and post-test measures. The participants were assessed after two weeks in which the randomly assigned participants within the three different groups had a positive affect between hassles group and gratitude group. The gratitude factor disappeared resulting in a difference in positive affect which was decreased by the affect in the hassles group. The journal writing intervention could be modified to include other techniques which could result in enhancing gratitude [7]. Longitudinal intervention based study demonstrated a significant effect on children's mental health in a one year experimental study. There was an increase in the wellbeing of mental health and a decrease in anxiety, depression and stress and distress symptoms. The symptoms persisted or only increased in the control group. Effective intervention techniques promoted self-esteem, optimism and other positive attitudes in students. This insisted the need for positive mental health inclusion in school setup. [8] A new model has been analyzed which is more than being grateful. Appreciating positive aspects in life can become a habit which goes hand in hand with gratitude. This paper focuses on subjective differences in well-being and gratitude in areas including psychopathology and other functional elements. Gratitude being causal, interventions to overcome limitations are studied and strategized. Biases, broaden and build principles, positive affect are discussed in relevance to the gratitude and well-being. Need for study as a necessity in clinical psychology is also justified [9]. In an organizational marketing service study, 239 employees in Korea participated to analyze the psychological wellbeing. Inherently being grateful has a very positive outlook in life. Hierarchical regression analysis and a convenience sampling were utilized for the analysis. Grateful disposition and social support on emotional dissonance had a positive effect on psychological well-being. Subjective affective traits are focused and given importance to this study hoping to reach the marketing industry [10]. Gratitude interventions is effective on physical health and health behaviors. Quality and efficacy of the outcome were evaluated in addition to the general relationship between gratitude and positive mental health. There has been many benefits of such interventions [11]. Gratitude influencing Subjective Well-being (SWB) is approached by two different frameworks. Cognitive and psychosocial mechanisms influence the well-being. This study reviews research papers which increase positive mental health and other symptoms of psychopathology. Evidences are limited although newer approaches to promote wellbeing could be effective. Yet again, this could be a driving force to bring about that change in improving the SWB in relation to Gratitude [12].

2. OBJECTIVES:

1. To determine the relationship between gratitude and well-being.
2. To identify the variables used in the researched papers
3. To understand the outcome of the interventions or studies
4. To find and focus on the research gap

3. METHODOLOGY:

A systematic approach was adopted to review the research papers. Several websites were looked up for reference majorly being ScienceDirect.com, Google Scholar, Pubmed, Mendeley, etc.

The purpose of the following study was to develop a reliable measurement of trait gratitude to successfully evaluate the relationship between gratitude and subjective well-being (SWB). 4 studies were conducted to test the accountability of GRAT, which is known for its consistency and stability. The results have also shown positive relations to SWB; 2 experiments conducted resulted in improved mood, and supported the predictability of GRAT. Gratitude is hence an affective trait important to SWB [13]. A qualitative analysis of gratitude and happiness in adolescents has reviewed how adolescents view gratitude. One such study analyzed essays written by a number of adolescents on this- the most recurring theme was Appreciation at 54.07% and Friendship at 21.18%. The analysis and understanding of adolescent perspectives can help with increasing potential happiness and wellbeing for them. Previous research shows that there indeed exists a difference and a relation between experiencing and expressing gratitude [14]

Two studies revealed that hope and happiness was predicted by gratitude. The first study showed that gratitude exceeded factors like patience, self-control and forgiveness in predicting happiness. In the second, gratitude related writing was conducted. Participants were to either write about a past hope that had been fulfilled, with gratitude; or write about a control condition. The first option resulted in a much higher increase in states of hope and happiness. This concludes that grateful remembering can boost happiness and future hope [15]. Gratitude has been explored as a virtue in a theoretical manner. Different traditions like Christianity, Judaism and Islamic origins of gratitude is explored and discussed. Every tradition has their own set of principles and approaches for practice. This study is also approached empirically to show the relationship between goal attainment and well-being. Leads are provided for future research in the same area [16]. Emmons & McCullough conducted reviews on the new and major developments in the measurement of gratitude across a person's lifespan. Research over the years has indicated that gratitude is vital for a person's overall well-being and good mental health. It is evident that from childhood to old age, gratitude plays a key role in psychological, physiological, and relational needs and requirements. It not only shows a boost in the positive aspects of a person's life such as health, happiness, and hope, but it also shows a decrease in negative aspects like problematic functioning [17]. When we look at moral emotions such as empathy, sympathy, guilt, and shame, we can see that gratitude exhibits a clear difference. We know that empathy and sympathy is the primary response one feels when faced with another person's distress; while guilt and shame are emotional responses of being unable to meet moral standards. Even as a trait, gratitude is different. It aims to notice the positive outcomes in life and results in a sense of pleasantness. When received with benefits, gratitude is the pleasant response of intrinsic thankfulness; regardless of whether that person is known or a stranger [18]. Another study talks about cultivating gratitude for a harvest of happiness. This evaluates the usefulness and importance of gratitude for human development and happiness, discussing various methods to improve this strength. Studies show that there is a clear correlation between wellbeing and gratitude and that it has a direct relationship with happiness. One method of enhancing gratitude is by getting trained to notice the good in a person's life and promote it by using positive appraisal techniques. While research shows how prominent gratitude is in the harvest of happiness, the cultivating of gratitude remains to be not that easy of a process [19]. To study the benefits of gratitude practice, this longitudinal intervention based research aims at finding the relationship between gratitude exercises and improved well-being. The intervention was a gratitude list based exercise for two weeks. Variables like trait gratitude, baseline depressive symptoms, inclusion of a rationale acted as moderators. Positive effect was shown in two week exercise minimalizing the negative effect and the depressive symptoms among the participants with an increase in the wellbeing [20]. About 1445 Chinese adolescents participated in a Happiness study for understanding the link gratitude to SWB. Social Support and Resilience acted as mediators to establish this link. It was found that there is not much difference between the two variables. However it established a strong relationship between them and gratitude [21]. Undergraduate university students and sample of individuals raised by custodial grandparents served as samples for a research to examine relationship between religiosity and well-being which may reduce symptoms for depression. This indicated that gratitude was an important factor in understanding the relation between religiosity and depressive symptoms and life satisfaction [22]. About 1445 Chinese adolescents participated in a Happiness study for understanding the link gratitude to SWB. Social Support and Resilience acted as mediators to establish this link. It was found that there is not much difference between the two variables. However it established a strong relationship between them and gratitude [21]. Undergraduate university students and sample of individuals

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4. FINDINGS/RESULTS:

Using the keywords like well-being, happiness, SWB, gratitude, intervention, happiness in different combinations yielded about 83 reviews. Well-being in association with money, economics and happiness were quite a many. After screening for gratitude and well-being, it brought down the related literature to about 45 reviews. This paper has utilized about 23 matching reviews.

- It has been found that the papers were examined in different ethnic background, different traditions and culture.
- Gratitude and its benefits
- Gratitude in an Indian context has sparsely been studied about. This gap has resulted the need for future study in this area.

5. CONCLUSION:

About 1445 Chinese adolescents participated in a Happiness study for understanding the link gratitude to SWB. Social Support and Resilience acted as mediators to establish this link. It was found that there is not much difference between the two variables. However it established a strong relationship between them and gratitude [21]. Undergraduate university students and sample of individuals raised by custodial grandparents served as samples for a research to examine relationship between religiosity and well-being which may reduce symptoms for depression. This indicated that gratitude was an important factor in understanding the relation between religiosity and depressive symptoms and life satisfaction [22]. Undergraduate university students and sample of individuals raised by custodial grandparents served as samples for a research to examine relationship between religiosity and well-being which may reduce symptoms for depression. This indicated that gratitude was an important factor in understanding the relation between religiosity and depressive symptoms and life satisfaction [22]. Expressing gratitude before COVID times were mostly handshake, an appropriate hug, pat on the back, etc. In this social distancing era, displaying emojis, emails, appreciative words, thumbs up signs have become a practice. Focusing on the moment of appreciation brings out joy and happiness around us. This way of expressing gratitude has a positive impact on others and our own well-being. This perspective of gratitude helps to energize, to heal and to hope. Mindfulness practice helps in coping with anxiety and uncertainty.

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